

CERVICAL OSTEOCHONDROSIS – THE “OFFICE DISEASE” OF THE 21ST CENTURY

Komilov Zafarbek Mirzaolimovich

Assistant at Central Asian Medical University.

e.mail: Zafarjonkomilov85@gmail.com.

Fergana, Uzbekistan

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ABSTRACT

Cervical osteochondrosis (degenerative changes in the cervical discs) is a relatively common condition among osteochondrosis. Osteochondrosis can occur in up to 50% of the middle-aged population. This disease is more common in people over 40 years of age, and is more common in professions associated with a sedentary lifestyle, lack of physical activity, and poor ergonomic habits.

Cervical osteochondrosis (degenerative changes in the cervical discs) is a relatively common condition among osteochondrosis. In general, cervical osteochondrosis can account for 20-30% of osteochondrosis. Lumbar osteochondrosis occurs (in more than 50% of cases). Osteochondrosis can occur in up to 50% of the middle-aged population. This disease is more common in people over 40 years old, and is more common in professions associated with a sedentary lifestyle, lack of physical activity, and poor ergonomic habits. According to medical statistics, symptoms of osteochondrosis are observed in 50-90% of the world's population. The average age of onset of osteochondrosis is 30-35 years. Under adverse conditions, symptoms of osteochondrosis can appear even earlier. In most cases, the patient is treated complaining of other (complications) symptoms.

Factors leading to osteochondrosis:

- Genetic predisposition. Plays a key role in the development of osteochondrosis in young patients;
- Age. Over the years, the amount of water in the spine decreases and the synthesis of connective tissue protein - proteoglycan deteriorates;
- Lack of physical activity - Intervertebral discs do not have their own blood vessels, but the vertebrae receive nutrients from blood vessels by diffusion. With physical inactivity, these processes slow down, which disrupts tissue trophism;
- Injury. From damage or injury to the vertebrae;
- Heavy lifting can lead to excessive compression of the intervertebral discs;
- Metabolic disorders. Endocrine diseases make it difficult to nourish tissues, which affects the condition of the spine;
- Staying in one position for a long time, performing physical exercises incorrectly, staying in a static position with your head bowed for a long time.

Prevention of cervical osteochondrosis. There are a number of exercises to prevent this type of osteochondrosis:

- Press your forehead to your palm and tighten your neck muscles. Do the exercise 3 times for 7 seconds. Then press the back of your head to your palm and hold for 3 times for 7 seconds;
- Press your left temple to your left palm, tighten your neck muscles, (3 times for 7 seconds), then press your right temple to your right palm, tighten your neck muscles (3 times for 7 seconds);
- Tilt your head back slightly. Press your chin to the hollow of your collarbone. Do the exercise at least 5 times;
- Keep your head and shoulders straight. Slowly turn your head as far as possible to the right (5 times). Turn it to the left (5 times);
- Lower your chin to your neck. First turn your head to the right 5 times, then to the left 5 times;
- Throw your head back. Try to touch your right ear to your right shoulder (5 times). Do the same with your left ear to your left shoulder (5 times);

It is recommended to perform these exercises during morning hygiene exercises, during the working day.

Swimming. Swimming on the back is the most effective. It is recommended to swim 2-3 times a week for 1-1.5 hours.

Self-massage - improves metabolic processes in muscles, ligaments and intervertebral discs, relieves muscle tension and reduces pain. For 10-15 minutes.

How to sit correctly.

- Avoid furniture that is too soft, Keep your body upright so that your body weight does not put excessive pressure on your spine.
 - The following requirements apply to furniture where you have to sit for a long time: the height of the chair or armchair should be at least knee-length and the length of the footrest, There should be enough space under the table for your legs;
 - If you have to sit for a long time, move around and change the position of your legs about every 15-20 minutes;
 - When sitting, make sure that your back is firmly attached to the back of the chair;
 - Sit correctly, without tilting your head too much and without bending your body, so as not to strain the muscles of the body;
 - Maintain optimal body weight;
 - If you work while sitting, you need to change your position every 1-1.5 hours;
 - Choose and wear comfortable shoes;
 - Sleep with an orthopedic mattress and pillow, properly organize your position;
 - Identify and correct incorrect posture - when walking or sitting;
- Ergonomic workplace. A table and chair that is suitable for height

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